

DEVELOPMENT EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article analyzes the experience of higher education systems in developed countries in the education system. Also, having studied foreign experience, a proposal was developed for the effective financing of higher education in our country.

Keywords : education , developing countries , model , modern , Germany

Financing of educational system is considered one of the most important part of expenditure contents of the government budget of Uzbekistan in the modernization processes of national economy. Furthermore, almost 30-35 percent of budget's expenditure is directed into higher education. Most assets from different non-budget funds are being spent for improvement of material-technical base of educational system's modernization. In spite of reforms in higher education in our country, our personal still have a great competitiveness in international trade market. This requires to bring up skilled cadres according to the international standards. To achieving this goal, firstly, they should be provided higher educational institutions according to the international standards and be supported comfortable conditions both students and teachers staff to improve their skills and research. From this point of view, creating sufficient directions of education financing and its practice is considered one of the most urgent issues these days. For solving these issues positively, country needs to introduce sufficient directions of education as well as financing sources. Learning education high developed countries experience is required in this way. After analyzing current education system and methods of its finance, it should be created sufficient fitted education system and its finance according to economic, political, financial, national current conditions of our country . These factors should be paid attention in creating national model of education systems model. There can be distinguished three kinds of education model in developed and developing countries:

- 1) Asian model;
- 2) American model;
- 3) European model.

Private sector has a great role in education finance in Asian model as well as the government. Schools are provided by municipal organs, government higher educational institutions are equal with private ones according to their numbers. Generally, local sources have more portion than national sources in finance of education. Schools and secondary schools are provided by the government freely, higher education is for a charge. Multifunctional system is created for students for covering this charge by scholarships or credits.

The modern scientific, technical and social progress requires constant renewal and even creating a qualitatively new system of higher professional education. New forms of learning can

be implemented through the provision of distance educational services through the modern technologies and the Internet. This is the way to raise the educational level of the population; to raise professional qualifications and to retrain specialists in various fields of knowledge. The paper presents the detailed analysis of researchers' reviews and special organizations' reports committed during 2000 – 2012 published in the United States, Europe and Asia. Research has shown that the experience of foreign distance education has a great application future in terms of the quality of modern vocational education in Russia development and improvement. The essential condition for the effective organization of educational activities in the system of education at the university is the study of the initial level of formation of this activity among students. Studying the learning skills of students at the beginning of their studies at a higher education institution makes it possible to concretize and empirically substantiate the main tasks of the purposeful formation of learning activities, the optimal forms and methods of teaching students as subjects of learning activities. In the process of linguistic training at the university on the basis of the subject-activity approach, the entire training system is focused on the student's personality and is structured in such a way that its activities, experience, worldview, learning and extracurricular interests and inclinations are taken into account when organizing communication in a foreign language. The path to finding the personal meaning of a student's activity also lies in taking his various interests into account. The student as a subject of educational and professional activity gradually realizes that all work is projected onto the development of thinking, culture of mental work, activity and cognitive independence of creative abilities. In the teaching of a foreign language, the subject-activity approach implies the organization and management of student's academic work as a subject of educational and professional activity in mastering various types of speech activity (listening, speaking, reading, writing), taking into account the characteristics and linguistic abilities of students. A foreign language course in a non-linguistic university is communicative, professionally-oriented, and aims to develop students' ability to exchange information in the field of professional activity. The understanding, transmission of content and the expression of meaning are of paramount importance. Under the communicative competence should be understood a high degree of training of a university graduate in certain types of foreign language speech activities: reading, writing, listening, speaking for the purposes of professional communication. After analyzed developed countries education system and its financing methods we can conclude that their models some directions may be used in our education system too. For instance, although in our country private institutes are allowed legally, there are no private institutes available for students and it lessens stable competition in education services market. If many accounts needing specialties are under the government provision and less account needing specialties are distributed by private sector such as in Japan it encourages to invest more money by private sector. Furthermore, private institutes should be given some facilities like in less tax fees or in taking licenses by the government. In our education system "dual principle" methods should be used like in Germany, which means theories time. Because it provides students to have not only theoretical knowledge but also practical knowledge at the same time. As a result, postgraduates have few problems when they begin their working experience and less time experience period. On the other hand, if institutions can appoints study fees by themselves, it may help to improve competitive environment among educational

institutions for attracting students. In my opinion, it helps to improve study quality as well as lessening study fees according to the large number of students.

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